

Beyond awareness: an assessment of reading program implementation in Butuan City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the levels of awareness and implementation of every child a reader program (ECARP) in public elementary schools within South Butuan District-I, Butuan City Division, Philippines. Additionally, it sought to determine the relationship between the awareness levels of teachers and school heads and the program's implementation. A mixed-method design was used, with survey questionnaires administered to 105 respondents, representing 95% of the district's teachers and school administrators. Analysis of the collected data revealed that participants exhibited high awareness regarding the components of implementation, monitoring, evaluation, and reading assessment. The implementation of ECARP was rated as very satisfactory. Furthermore, a significant relationship was identified between the levels of awareness and implementation, underscoring the importance of guideline awareness for effective program execution. The study concludes that heightened awareness of ECARP guidelines is crucial for achieving a well-implemented reading program. These findings offer a valuable contribution to the field of education by providing a localized analysis of the reading program, highlighting both its challenges and successes. The study introduces data that can inform future policy adjustments, while offering new insights for enhancing existing reading programs and guiding the development of localized intervention plans.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Reading is the most fundamental skill that learners need to acquire at an early age [1]. It empowers students to expand their understanding, refine their thinking, and ignite their creativity [2]. However, improving the reading abilities of Filipino students remain a challenge for educators and policymakers. Despite government efforts, recent studies show many students still struggle with reading comprehension, vocabulary, and critical thinking [3]. Developing reading skills in young children is essential for enhancing educational outcomes and has significant long-term impacts. Proficient readers can become valuable economic assets for their countries [4].

Despite the known link between reading competence and economic growth [4], the 2018 PISA results showed that 80% of Filipino 15-year-olds failed to meet the minimum reading proficiency level, scoring lower than most participating countries [5]. The Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines introduced the every child a reader program (ECARP) which tasks the teachers in making every learner becomes a reader appropriate to their grade level [6]. This initiative aligns with the K-12 basic education program, which emphasizes the development of competitive literacy skills among Filipino learners [7].

The DepEd, through the ECARP, strives to ensure that every child becomes a grade-level reader and writer, supporting the education for all (EFA) goal of universal school participation and reducing dropouts and repetition [8], and ensures that no one is left behind. Therefore, teachers must implement effective strategies to support struggling readers [9]. The implementation of ECARP has been adapted in various ways across different organizational levels [10].

The South Butuan District-I of Butuan City Division conducted Operation Pabasa in addition to the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) pre-test and post-test. The results revealed that 285 pupils were considered non-readers during the pre-test. Because of this, the district conducted a program implementation review (PIR) on the school heads accountability on reading enhancement (SHARE) project in order to monitor the reading performance of the pupils and to assess the effectiveness of school reading flagships of the different schools in the district.

In addition, the South-I District conducted the learning action cell sessions on early language, literacy, and numeracy (ELLN) program. This program helps equip the teachers and instructional leaders in basic literacy and numeracy knowledge and pedagogical skills [11]. The district had also successfully launched the Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiative) following DepEd Memorandum No. 173 s. 2019. This strengthens the implementation, goal, and enhancement of ECARP to answer the country's reading problem based on PISA results [12].

There are challenges in implementing reading interventions that are aligned with ECARP such as possibility of reduced support from stakeholders, and limitations in the availability of diverse resources, which could affect the breadth of learning opportunities for students [13]. One study emphasizes the significance of joint efforts among teachers, parents, and the local government unit (LGU) in tackling reading challenges [14]. Despite the widespread implementation of ECARP, its effectiveness and the awareness among school administrators and teachers need evaluation. Many pupils still struggle with early language and literacy standards despite various reading interventions. Studies have highlighted gaps in implementation, such as inconsistencies in teacher training, resource allocation, and stakeholders' involvement.

The overarching problem guiding this study is: to what extent do the awareness levels of educators and administrators influence the effective implementation of the ECARP in South Butuan District-I? This research aims to address this question by exploring key dimensions of ECARP, specifically the levels of awareness and implementation in the areas of program implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and reading assessment; the relationship between awareness and implementation; best practices employed by schools; and the challenges encountered during the program's implementation. By investigating these factors, this study seeks to identify the elements that contribute to the success of ECARP and offer actionable insights for improving its effectiveness in public elementary schools.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

This study employed a mixed-methods design. According to Creswell [15], this approach focuses on collecting, analyzing, and integrating both quantitative and qualitative data within a single study or series of studies. Furthermore, Adu *et al.* [16] noted that this method offers a more comprehensive understanding of research problems than using either approach alone. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency count and weighted mean, were applied to summarize participants' levels of awareness and the extent of program implementation. For inferential analysis, Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationship between awareness and implementation. The qualitative component aimed to provide deeper insights into educators' perceptions, experiences, and challenges regarding program implementation. The thematic analysis was employed to systematically categorize qualitative data, identifying recurring themes and patterns that further supported the quantitative findings [17].

This study employed a survey questionnaire aligned with DepEd Order No. 50, s. 2012 [18], covering five areas: implementation, monitoring and evaluation, reading assessment, best practices, and challenges in executing the ECARP. The survey was designed to gauge teachers' and school administrators' awareness and implementation levels, with items tailored to ECARP's core components as outlined in DepEd guidelines. A panel of education experts reviewed the instrument to ensure content relevance or validity and alignment with study objectives. A pilot test with a separate group of teachers and school administrators assessed the survey's clarity and reliability, leading to minor adjustments for clarity. Cronbach's alpha values confirmed the instrument's high reliability, ensuring it produced meaningful data for analysis.

2.2. Sampling design

The participants in the study comprised 95% of the total population of elementary teachers, including school reading coordinators and school administrators, in South Butuan District I. A total of 105 participants were included, consisting of 94 teachers and 11 school administrators. The simple random

sampling through lottery technique was used to identify the actual participants of the study. According to Daniel and Cross [19], when determining the sample size needed for a desired level of accuracy, researchers are advised to use the maximum variability assumption, often at 50%, to ensure robustness. However, in this study, the researchers opted for a 95% sample of the target population to enhance representativeness and ensure comprehensive insights from the teachers and school administrators directly involved in program implementation. The sample size also aligns with the study's context, considering economic and logistical constraints imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic [20], [21]. Health and safety protocols limited in-person interactions and made it impractical to engage with the entire population, as many educators were operating remotely. This sampling approach allowed for a feasible and representative analysis without disrupting participants' responsibilities, as educators adapted to hybrid teaching demands. Given the urgency to evaluate the ECARP program under pandemic conditions, this sample size enabled timely data collection and analysis while ensuring meaningful results. The school reading coordinators are selected as one of the participants of the study since they are knowledgeable on the program based on the trainings and experiences they have gone through. They are the one who keep all the consolidated records of the pupils' reading profile and report it to the school head. They are also in-charge of making after activity reports on reading related activities. Further, class advisers were included in the study since they are considered as reading teachers in their respective classrooms. They are the one who administer the reading programs, projects, interventions and reading assessments directly to the pupils. Finally, the school administrators were included as participants of the study since they are the one who lead and supervise the implementation of all school-based ECARP activities. They are also the one who give technical assistance to the teachers.

2.3. Data gathering procedure

The researchers asked permission from the public schools district supervisor and public elementary school principals of South Butuan District I to allow them to conduct the study. An online survey form was used to gather the data. Hence, a letter asking permission was also stated in the online form. The responses recorded were checked and monitored to ensure 100% responses. The data were tallied, tabulated, processed and submitted to the statistician for analysis and interpretation.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The level of awareness on ECARP in the public elementary schools in terms of implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and reading assessment

Figure 1 presents the level of awareness on ECARP in the public elementary schools. In the implementation component, the findings show that the designation of school reading coordinator garnered the highest mean of 4.83. This implies that the participants have extensive knowledge along this line. On the other hand, the participation of the students in the planning process got the lowest mean of 3.59 or highly aware which is described as moderately extensive.

Figure 1. Level of awareness on ECARP

The overall weighted mean on the level of awareness of the participants in the ECARP implementation is 4.16 or highly aware which is described as moderately extensive. The data corroborate that the participants are generally highly aware on the implementation of ECARP. This further reveal that the teachers are well-informed about how ECARP is being carried out in their respective schools. Implementing engaging reading programs and strategies is essential for elementary school coordinators to reveal student reading engagement [22]. The Department of Education Republic of the Philippines [23] reiterated that reading coordinators will manage the reading literacy initiatives in their respective schools. They will also serve as consultants to teachers. Moreover, Narbonito [22] stressed that learners should explore ways to enhance their reading engagement experience, benefiting not just themselves but also their teachers.

In the monitoring and evaluation component, the indicator which states that the school includes reading program's monitoring and evaluation in the reading action plan garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.30 or highly aware which is described as moderately extensive. Meanwhile, the indicator which indicates that the school allocates funds for the periodic monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of early reading interventions got the lowest weighted mean of 3.86 or highly aware which is also described as moderately extensive. In general, the overall weighted mean on the level of awareness of the participants under the monitoring and evaluation is 4.12 or highly aware which indicates that they have moderate awareness on it. The result reveals that the participants are knowledgeable about the inclusion of reading program's monitoring and evaluation in the reading action plan as it is part of their planning activity. However, they do not totally assume that they can make budget for the implementation of this activity. This may be due to lack of dissemination of budget allocation in the schools or may be due to teachers' showing low interest or being hesitant in asking for school funding. This finding contrasts with the study by Magdalena *et al.* [24] which suggests that schools utilize various strategies to achieve the school literacy movement, including the allocation of funds through independent school funds or regional revenue and expenditure budget/school operational assistance. Further, according to Prasetia and Adlan [25], conducting evaluation assess the effectiveness of the school's literacy program in achieving its intended outcomes to improve reading culture in elementary schools.

In terms of reading assessment, the indicator which states that the school administers reading assessment (pre and post PHIL-IRI reading assessment) garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.81 which signifies very extensive awareness on it. On the other hand, indicator that states that the school develops localized assessment tools garnered the lowest weighted mean of 3.90 which signifies moderate extensive awareness to the program. The overall weighted mean is 4.26 or highly aware which signifies that level of awareness of the participants in reading assessment is moderately extensive. The result reveals that the participants are very much aware of the conduct of the reading assessments like pre and post PHIL-IRI and operation Pabasa- usually done by school heads. This will identify the entry performance of the students and how far they have gone through with reading within the school year. In addition, this will also assess the effectiveness of strategies and instructional reading materials used by the teachers in addressing certain issues relevant to student's reading performance. However, developing localized assessment tools has the least emphasis in schools. This may be due to the lack of teachers' training on developing localized assessment tools. This contradicts the study of Llarena [26] that reveals principals monitored the implementation of reading programs using their own localized forms and generic monitoring tools for all programs. Contextualization of pre and post-reading materials will support the need to evaluate the reading levels based on the learning platform utilized by the learners. Further, Geonzon [27] also pointed out that one of the significant obstacles to the successful implementation of DepEd's language programs is the lack of adequate training for teachers. ECARP, as highlighted by Department of Education Republic of the Philippines [18], recognizes the need for localized versions of the standardized Early Grades Reading Assessment (EGRA) to obtain reliable and valid data on children's reading abilities.

3.2. The level of implementation on ECARP in the public elementary schools in terms of implementation, monitoring and evaluation, and reading assessment

Figure 2 shows the level of implementation on ECARP in the public elementary schools. In the implementation component, the indicator which states that the school designates School Reading Coordinator garnered the highest weighted mean of 4.70 that can be described as outstanding which signifies that the schools have implemented the mentioned guideline very well. On the other hand, indicator which states that the students participate in the planning process garnered the lowest weighted mean of 3.63 that can be described as very satisfactory and signifies that the guideline is well implemented. Generally, the overall weighted mean on the level of implementation of the participants under the implementation is 4.11 or very satisfactory. The findings reveal that the schools have implemented the program well. This implies that schools have practiced the designation of the reading coordinator. Department of Education Republic of the Philippines [18] points that teachers play a crucial role in supporting literacy activities by providing essential resources such as books, reading corners, posters, motivational quotes, and a variety of text-rich materials.

However, the findings also implies that there is less emphasis on letting the students participate in the planning process. Teacher-student interactions, feedback mechanisms, and peer learning emerged as key strategies employed by English teachers to enhance student engagement in reading activities [28].

Figure 2. Level of implementation on ECARP

In terms of second component (monitoring and evaluation), the participants have implemented well the indicator which states that the school conducts regular periodic monitoring and evaluation of early reading interventions as evident of having the weighted mean of 4.28. On the other hand, the indicator which states that the school allocates funds for the periodic monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of early reading interventions garnered the lowest weighted mean of 3.94 which signifies well implementation to it. In general, the overall weighted mean on the level of implementation of the participants under the monitoring and evaluation is 4.10 or very satisfactory. This signifies that the school has implemented the ECARP guidelines well. Sulfemi [29] noted that to ensure comprehensive program evaluation, it is recommended that both the literacy team and the principal participate, as the teacher's role as a model for literacy activities is still developing. Evaluating reading activities is crucial for achieving learning objectives, as reading comprehension is fundamental to academic success across all subject areas [30].

In terms of the third component (reading assessment), the participants show outstanding implementation with a weighted mean of 4.73 in indicator that states that the school administers reading assessments (pre and post PHIL-IRI reading assessment). On the other hand, in the indicator which states that the school develops localized assessment tools garnered the lowest weighted mean of 3.92 which signifies very satisfactory or well implementation to it. While the school's development of localized assessment tools received low rating, integrating cultural content into language learning [31] could further enhance the program by addressing diverse learning needs and fostering cultural awareness. Generally, the overall weighted mean on the level of implementation of the participants under the reading assessment is 4.24 or very satisfactory. The results reveal that the participants have implemented the reading assessments well. While schools should contextualize reading programs, Lucero *et al.* [32] emphasizes the importance of parental involvement in supporting student reading development, recognizing that reading success encompasses not only skills but also behavioral and emotional aspects best understood by parents.

3.3. Significant relationship between the level of awareness and level of implementation of ECARP

The results of inferential analysis using correlation analysis to see the relationship between the level of awareness and level of implementation of ECARP are shown in Table 1. Based on Table 1, a significance value of 0.000 is obtained, so it can be concluded that the level of awareness has a relationship with the level of implementation, because the significance value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05. The Pearson correlation value is positive 0.9070. This positive value indicates a positive relationship. The correlation value of 0.9070 shows high positive correlation of the level of awareness and level of implementation. This implies that teacher's awareness about the guidelines of ECARP leads to the well-execution of the implementation of the program. It can be understood as well that teachers, reading coordinators and school administrators are very responsive to the directives from the higher office.

Table 1. Correlation analysis between the level of awareness and level of implementation of ECARP in the public schools

Variables	Mean	SD	r	Interpretation	Sig. (2-Tailed)	Significance
Level of awareness	4.1787	0.57593	0.9070**	High positive correlation	0.000	Significant
Level of implementation	4.1591	0.59475				

**correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The data further shows that they valued ECARP by implementing the guidelines embedded to such program. However, to further enhance the program's effectiveness, Abejuela *et al.* [33] recommends a comprehensive reassessment of ECARP through regular monitoring and a strengthened evaluation of assessment tools and reading activities in alignment with the K to 12 curriculum guide. While school personnel demonstrate a strong commitment to ECARP implementation, addressing early reading difficulties remains crucial for long-term academic success.

Study by Manurung *et al.* [34] highlighted that employing a range of reading strategies, including problem-solving, support, and global approaches, significantly improves students' reading comprehension. It stressed the need to raise students' awareness of effective strategies to enhance their understanding of texts. Similarly, Moneba and Lovitos [35] in the Davao Region recommended implementing a comprehensive reading program focused on developing critical and applied skills to improve reading comprehension, particularly for students with special needs. The study also suggested allocating funds for learning resource centers, ensuring the availability of quality-assured intervention materials, and encouraging parental involvement in reading activities at home. Additionally, it proposed orienting parents and guardians on proper word pronunciation to help them support their children's reading practices more effectively.

Further, Lamsen [36] emphasizes the need for collaborative efforts to secure funding for essential reading programs and resources. Effective school leadership, as highlighted by Llarena [26], involves providing ongoing support, resources, and guidance to teachers, partners, and learners, empowering them to plan and implement successful reading activities. The positive correlation between effective school literacy initiatives and increased student engagement in reading [37] underscores the importance of government and school administration support for such initiatives. This support as suggested by Wulyani *et al.* [38] include providing teachers and students with essential resources, such as graded readers and structured extensive reading activities, to facilitate a robust reading culture within schools. Moreover, Lamsen [36] noted that early reading challenges can lead to lasting academic difficulties, recommending that school leaders and teachers should collaborate to secure funding for materials and snacks for reading program beneficiaries.

3.4. The best practices/initiatives of the public elementary schools on ECARP

There are plenty of practices done by the South Butuan District-I elementary schools to rigorously implement the ECARP. Such practices had helped the schools attain the objectives of the program. The best practices identified were the conduct of early reading interventions, establishment of school reading centers, integration of technology in teaching reading, teacher's involvement in seminars, reporting of reading assessment results to the parents and the strong support coming from the stakeholders.

For the conduct of early intervention programs, schools found that students have reading problems even at the early time of the school year, so they take initiative to conduct interventions. This claim is corroborated by the statements of teachers and school administrators. A teacher (participant 5) stated, "*A teacher-pupil tutorial in reading beyond school hours for the slow readers.*" Also, another teacher (participant 6) expressed, "*Remedial reading every afternoon, have a little teacher or peer reading tutorial.*" A school administrator (participant 4) said: "*The teachers conduct reading intervention before the class in the morning and after class in the afternoon or before going home by reading a story and videoke. Teachers also give awards to the pupils.*" Also, one school administrator (participant 5) said:

"One of the school's best practices is that we identify the reading ability of the pupils in the early months of the classes then give them activities as our intervention including but not limited to one on one coaching, remediation session, parent coaching, peer tutoring and at the end of every month we will assess learners through reading Festival in which all pupils belong to slow and non-reader will be competing each other and we will give them rewards after the contest."

For the establishment of school reading centers, schools claim that having a sound environment and appropriate reading instructional materials will help the teachers and students during the conduct of reading remediation. This claim is supported by the statements of teachers and school administrators. One teacher (participant 8) said, "*One best practices, the school has a reading center with a sets of reading materials.*" Another teacher (participant 9) stated:

“Use of ICT based approach in improving the reading skills of the pupils especially for the higher grade learners. For the lower grade learners, the teacher gives more focus on the slow readers by giving various reading materials and reading exercises to motivate them to read.”

For the involvement of teachers in training, schools find a way to enhance the skills of the teachers in teaching reading which is also vital in achieving quality instruction. So, teachers were sent to seminars for them to be equipped with new pedagogy in teaching reading. This assertion is supported by the statements of teachers and school administrators. A school administrator (participant 3) stated:

“As a school head in our school I let my teachers attend any seminars and training related to reading programs to help them develop their ability to teach children effectively.”

As to the reporting of reading assessment results to the parents, schools diligently inform the parents about the reading status of their child will help the parents become aware of their child’s reading performance in school. This statement is being verified by the teachers and school administrators. A teacher (participant 13) stated:

“The best practice that our school implemented is always tapping and communicating the parents about the performance of each pupil in terms of reading.”

For the strong support coming from the stakeholders, the school may find difficult to implement ECARP activities alone. Thus, the schools find the best way to tap the stakeholders who would help in realizing the program. This claim is being supported by the teachers and school administrators. A teacher (participant 39) stated:

“The Barangay council is one of our partners in the implementation of our school reading programs and interventions. The council conducts monthly feeding and Pabasa through their program ‘Oplan Tutok kaon-Basa’.”

Also, a school administrator (participant 3) said:

“Feeding Program sponsored by the teachers and parents every other day, peer tutorial, parent teacher, and the implementation of class reading projects in response to the school reading program.”

This implies that schools have established a strong coordination with the stakeholders to achieve better implementation of the program.

3.5. The challenges encountered in the implementation of ECARP

The schools encountered several challenges in the implementation of the program which include the lack of parents’ instructional support, absenteeism, teachers’ availability, and allocation of funds. For the lack of parents’ instructional support, even though the schools have already tapped the parents, others are still unresponsive. This resulted to the lack of instructional support to their children. This is being affirmed by a teacher (participant 34) stated:

“Maybe the parents of the children because some of the parents when their child is at home already, they do not help them, so how will the child improve if the parents have no concern.”

As to the absenteeism, the school finds a negative effect on the reading performance of the student - absentees. Thus, this is being considered as one of the hindrances in the implementation of the program. This claim is being affirmed by the teachers and school administrators. Participant 71) stated, *“Absenteeism due to health condition, child labor, and financial problem.”* Another teacher (participant 52) said:

“Absenteeism and lack of support from parents in the reading practices hence some of the parents are non-readers themselves.”

A school administrator also stated:

“Not all parents in the community can help their children at home because they too are non-readers.”

A teacher (participant 17) also stated:

“When a pupil is always absent. then he/she doesn’t know how to read.”

For the teachers’ availability, there were times that the teachers failed to implement the activity properly because of some other related works that need to be done. This is being affirmed by the teachers. A teacher-participant said, *“Overlapping of activities and teachers being assigned to many coordinatorship.”*

For the allocation of funds, some of the materials needed in implementing the activities were not realized because of the lack of budget. This claim is being supported by the teachers and administrators. A teacher (participant 35) said, *“Allocation of funds for the continuity of the project conducted and more in the reproduction of the LR materials.”* A school administrator (participant 3) also stated:

“The challenges are, budget are not enough to provide conducive learning reading center for our student because we have to use the funds wisely to cater all the needs of the school/student that’s why we cannot implement the 100% for the activities right away but as time goes by we did our best to supplement the needs of our children through utilizing materials available in our school and with the support of the community as well.”

This implies that the problems encountered in schools do not remain as problems. The schools find solutions to address them so that the ECARP will be effectively implemented. Compean-Garcia [39] revealed that parents’ perspectives on the early literacy skills of bilingual learners significantly influence their children’s literacy development. Moreover, parents not only express interest but actively participate in fostering their children’s early literacy experiences. This suggests that parents from language-minority backgrounds are both capable and eager to support their children’s academic success. Consequently, teacher training programs should prioritize strategies to strengthen collaboration between parents and educators, enabling schools to effectively leverage the support available in the home environment.

In addition, the study by Agustin and Belarmino [40] found that excessive absenteeism among pupils negatively impacts their reading comprehension. The study highlighted parental involvement as a crucial factor in learners’ educational progress and underscored the need to raise parents’ awareness of their vital role in fostering academic success. In the study of Polongasa II [41], to address issues like student absenteeism, respondent schools implemented strategies such as feeding programs, home visits, and parent orientations to engage parents and address the challenges affecting their children.

Moreover, Mang’uu *et al.* [42] suggested that school principals should ensure sufficient teaching and learning resources are available while also managing teachers’ workloads effectively. It emphasized the importance of principals collaborating closely with teachers to provide adequate teaching materials and e-resources to support both educators and students. To address budget constraints, Polongasa II [41] noted that respondents suggested conducting fundraising activities and providing training and workshops on budgeting and financial support. Encouraging stakeholders to actively participate in school activities and projects is essential, as their involvement serves as a vital partnership that contributes to the success and improvement of learners’ academic performance.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings of this study highlight that public elementary schools in South Butuan District-I are highly aware of ECARP’s core components—implementation, monitoring, and evaluation, and reading assessment—and exhibit very satisfactory implementation levels. A strong positive correlation was found between awareness and implementation, emphasizing that informed teachers and administrators play a critical role in the program’s success. Despite these achievements, challenges such as insufficient parental involvement, absenteeism, teacher availability, and funding constraints hinder the program’s full potential. Addressing these barriers through targeted interventions, such as parental training, additional teacher resources, and sustainable funding initiatives, can significantly enhance ECARP outcomes.

This study is limited to South Butuan District-I and focuses primarily on teachers’ and administrators’ perspectives. Future research could expand to other districts, incorporate a larger sample size, and examine additional variables, such as student outcomes. It is recommended that DepEd strengthen teacher training, allocate consistent funding for reading resources, and promote collaboration among schools, parents, and stakeholders. These steps will ensure that ECARP continues to address reading challenges effectively and foster improved literacy outcomes across public elementary schools.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

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R : Resources

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E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

INFORMED CONSENT

We have obtained informed consent from all individuals included in this study.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The research related to human use has been complied with all the relevant national regulations and institutional policies in accordance with the tenets of the Helsinki Declaration and has been approved by the authors' institutional review board or equivalent committee.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author [JFC], upon reasonable request.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. D. Pasigna, "Effectiveness of the Teacher-Made Individualized Learning Kit in Beginning Reading to the Performance of Kindergarten Learners in Phonemic and Phonological Awareness," *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies (IJAMS)*, vol. 3, no. 10, pp. 302–316, 2023.
- [2] A. Azmar, Neliwati, and M. Rifa'i, "Library Service Management to Enhance Students' Reading Interest at State Senior High School 1 Secanggang, Langkat Regency," *EDUTECH: Journal of Education and Technology*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 506–517, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.29062/edu.v7i2.619.
- [3] M. V. Idulog *et al.*, "Filipino Students' Reading Abilities: A Note on the Challenges and Potential Areas for Improvement," *International Journal of Education and Teaching Zone*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 233–242, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.57092/ijetz.v2i2.128.
- [4] M. T. Boltron and A. L. Ramos, "Improving Beginning Reading Literacy through Marungko Approach," *ASEAN Journal of Basic and Higher Education*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2021.
- [5] M. J. L. Tomas, E. T. Villaros, and S. M. A. Galman, "The Perceived Challenges in Reading of Learners: Basis for School Reading Programs," *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 107–122, 2021, doi: 10.4236/jss.2021.95009.

- [6] N. T. Rubin and A. S. Traverro, "Fostering reading level and story comprehension through MARITES (Marungko Approach Reading Intervention to Elementary Schoolers) with mentor-mentee arrangement," *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, & Management (IRJSTEM)*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 18–25, 2022.
- [7] J. Ann, B. Roque, M. G. Javillonar, M. N. Pascua, and M. B. Cruzat, "Revisiting Filipino Pupils' Reading Ability Post-Pandemic: Basis for a Remediation Program," *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Publications (IJMRAP)*, vol. 5, no. 8, pp. 54–58, 2023.
- [8] C. H. G. Misanes and E. R. Pascual, "Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) Performance of Grade 8 Students: Basis for a Reading Intervention Program," *Psychology and Education: a Multidisciplinary Journal*, vol. 13, pp. 276–289, 2023.
- [9] J. M. Pocaan, L. L. Bailon, and J. P. T. Pocaan, "Strategic reading intervention for left-behind learners in the Philippines," *LLT Journal: A Journal on Language and Language Teaching*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 367–378, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.24071/llt.v25i2.5087.
- [10] D. A. M. Telmo, "A Case Study Report on a School-based Reading Program Based on the Every-Child-A-Reader Program (ECARP)," M.S. thesis, University of the Philippines Open University, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines, 2020.
- [11] I. B. Gaviño and E. N. Chua, "Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy (ELLN) Program in Promoting Salient Teaching-Learning Outcomes in a Distance Learning Realm," *International Journal of Research Publications*, vol. 106, no. 1, pp. 50–58, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.47119/IJRP1001061820223708.
- [12] L. M. Tabuyo, "PROJECT ELL (Enhancing Literacy Skills of Learners through Audio-Visual Delivery) and Reading Comprehension Among Grade5 Pupils of San Roque Elementary School," *Studies in Technology and Education*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 62–70, 2023.
- [13] J. D. Engada and G. Maguate, "PROJECT LEARNDEMIC (Learning Assessment and Reading Development through Enhanced Modified Intervention and Collaboration)," *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, vol. 11, no. 9, pp. 31–41, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.18535/ijprm/v11i09.ee01.
- [14] M. O. Salibay, "Enhancing Literacy: A Comparative Analysis of the Effectiveness of Project Bear and Arangkada Pagbasa Reading Interventions in Claver National High School (S.Y. 2022-2024)," *Advances in Research*, vol. 25, no. 1, pp. 54–64, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.9734/air/2024/v25i11018.
- [15] J. W. Creswell, "Mixed-method research: Introduction and application," in *Handbook of Educational Policy*, G. J. Cizek, Ed. San Diego, CA: Academic Press, 1999, pp. 455–472, doi: 10.1016/B978-012174698-8/50045-X.
- [16] J. Adu, M. F. Owusu, E. Martin-Yeboah, L. A. P. Gavidia, and S. Gyamfi, "A discussion of some controversies in mixed methods research for emerging researchers," *Methodological Innovations*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 321–330, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1177/20597991221123398.
- [17] V. Braun and V. Clarke, "Using thematic analysis in psychology," *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 77–101, Jan. 2006, doi: 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa.
- [18] Department of Education Republic of the Philippines, "DO 50, s. 2012 – Guidelines on the Utilization of Funds for the Every Child a Reader Program (ECARP)," 2012. [Online]. Available: <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/06/15/do-50-s-2012-guidelines-on-the-utilization-of-funds-for-the-every-child-a-reader-program-ecarp/>
- [19] W. W. Daniel and C. L. Cross, *Biostatistics: A Foundation for Analysis in the Health Sciences*, 10th ed. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2018.
- [20] A. Onwuegbuzie and K. Collins, "A Typology of Mixed Methods Sampling Designs in Social Science Research," *The Qualitative Report*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 281–316, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.46743/2160-3715/2007.1638.
- [21] M. Kaur, "Application of mixed method approach in public health research," *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 93–97, 2016, doi: 10.4103/0970-0218.173495.
- [22] I. J. D. Narbonito, "Unveiling Student Reading Engagement: Role of Elementary School Coordinators," *International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Studies (IJAMS)*, vol. 4, no. 6, pp. 158–167, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ijams-bbp.net/archive/vol-4-issue-6-june/unveiling-student-reading-engagement-role-of-elementary-school-coordinators/>
- [23] Department of Education Republic of the Philippines, "DM 173, s. 2019 – Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3Bs Initiative)," 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2019/11/22/november-22-2019-dm-173-s-2019-hamon-bawat-bata-bumabasa-3bs-initiative/>
- [24] I. Magdalena, M. Akbar, and R. Situmorang, "Evaluation of The Implementation of The School Literacy Movement in Elementary Schools in The District and City of Tangerang," *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 537–546, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.18415/ijmmu.v6i4.1029.
- [25] I. Prasetia and M. Adlan, "Management of the Literacy Movement Program (LMP) to Improve Reading Culture in Elementary Schools," *Journal of Innovation in Educational and Cultural Research*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 316–322, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.46843/jiecr.v3i3.117.
- [26] Z. G. Llarena, "Exploring the Roles of School Heads in the Implementation of Reading Programs," *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 60–64, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.36713/epri12848.
- [27] R. Geonzon, "Implementation of the Department of Education's Language Programs for Public Elementary Schools," *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 1128–1142, 2024.
- [28] S. R. Contaoli, "Reading Engagement Strategies in Blended Learning Context," *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1–13, May 2024, doi: 10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i03.19771.
- [29] W. B. Sulfemi, "Management of School Literacy with Students' Interest in Reading," *Education & Learning in Developing Nations*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 62–67, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.26480/eldn.02.2023.62.67.
- [30] R. Manlapaz, S. Cabahug, and M. I. Divina, "Contextualized Based-Learning Materials: an Evaluation to Enhance the Reading Comprehension of the Grade 7 Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic," *Psychology and Education: a Multidisciplinary Journal*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1269–1276.
- [31] A. Panklam and S. Kaowiwattanakul, "From Globalization to Localization: Promoting EFL Students' Reading Comprehension Using GFOS Model Based on Collaborative Learning Approach," *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, vol. 14, no. 9, pp. 2791–2801, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.17507/tpls.1409.15.
- [32] N. E. Lucero, M. B. Reboquillo, J. P. Nieves, F. M. Tubice, S. S. Ibao, and F. Escartin, "Managing the Implementation and Evaluation of the School Reading Program," *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 1–10, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.9734/ajess/2019/v5i430151.
- [33] H. J. Abejuela, K. Akut, A. S. Del Rosario, and C. Balane, "Assessment of the Reading Curriculum in Basic Education in the Philippines Context," *International Journal of Language Education*, vol. 1, no. 1, p. 26, 2023, doi: 10.26858/ijole.v1i1.23641.
- [34] S. Manurung, A. Ariyanti, D. Yana, J. B. Sinaga, and A. Adam, "The Correlation between Reading Strategies and Reading Comprehension," *JCP (Jurnal Cahaya Pendidikan)*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 221–231, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.33373/chypend.v9i2.5975.
- [35] A.-J. N. Moneba and A. H. R. Lovitos, "Reading Attitude and Learning Motivation as Predictors of Reading Comprehension," *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 185–199, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.9734/ajess/2024/v50i41322.

- [36] M. E. L. Lamsen, "Pupils' Reading Achievement and Innovative Reading Strategies: Basis for Enhanced Implementation of School Reading Program." *International Journal of Research Publications*, vol. 124, no. 1, pp. 1326–1331, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.47119/IJRP1001241520234893.
- [37] R. Lolotandung and T. Trivena, "Literacy Program to Increase Reading interest in Third-Grade Elementary School Students," *Edumaspu: Jurnal Pendidikan*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 1778–1782, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.33487/edumaspu.v6i2.4454.
- [38] A. N. Wulyani, U. Widiati, and N. El Khoiri, "Challenges in implementing extensive reading (ER) programs: Voices from English teachers at Indonesian secondary schools," *Pegeg Journal of Education and Instruction*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 74–83, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.47750/pegegog.12.01.08.
- [39] N. Compean-Garcia, "Early Literacy Experiences in the Home: A Parent's Perspective," *Journal of Border Educational Research*, vol. 9, no. 2005, pp. 23–36, 2011. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mendeley.com/catalogue/415daf02-efae-38c8-b634-23170a6a9e48/>
- [40] L. J. Agustin and M. P. Belarmino, "Factors Affecting the Reading Comprehension of Grade 2 Learners: Basis for an Intervention Program," *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–12, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.36948/ijfmr.2024.v06i01.12619.
- [41] S. M. Polongasa II, "Determinants of Performance of Public Elementary Schools Division of Agusan del Norte, Philippines," *SMCC Higher Education Research Journal*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 101–121, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.18868/md-v9-a8.
- [42] N. S. Mang'uu, P. Maithya, and M. Kimani, "Effects of Availability of Teaching and Learning Resources on Teacher Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Kitui County, Kenya," *European Journal of Education Studies*, vol. 8, no. 9, pp. 248–272, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.46827/ejes.v8i9.3908.

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